

AISTER

WP2A3 Synthesis of Key Findings – Roundtables

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Abstract:	This synthesis consolidates the key findings from three expert roundtables organised under WP2A2 of the AISTER project in 2025. Discussions explored the opportunities and risks of using artificial intelligence for safeguarding cultural heritage in crisis contexts, including documentation, data management, and citizen engagement. Ethical concerns, preparedness challenges, and inequalities of access were highlighted, alongside the critical role of communities in emergency response. A four-phase framework – mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery – was identified as a guiding structure. Recommendations include integrating AI ethics into curricula, promoting small-scale open models,

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strengthening community resilience, and prioritising pre-crisis digitisation.

AI, cultural heritage, crisis response, citizen science, ethics, preparedness, resilience, Ukraine, digital preservation

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISTER	AI-enabled Citizen Participation in University-driven Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Safeguarding
DARIAH ERIC	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities – European Research Infrastructure Consortium
NGO	Non-governmental organization
UL	University of Latvia
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNILU	University of Luxembourg
W2L	Web2Learn
WP2A2 / WP2A3	Work Package 2, Activity 2 / Activity 3

Executive Summary

This synthesis report presents the key findings from three expert roundtables organised in 2025 within the framework of the AISTER project (*AI-enabled Citizen Participation in University-driven Ukrainian Cultural Heritage Safeguarding*). The project, funded under Erasmus+, brings together partners from Latvia, Luxembourg, Greece, Ukraine, and the Netherlands to explore how artificial intelligence (AI) and citizen science can strengthen the protection of cultural heritage in times of crisis.

The roundtables were a three-angle perspective in ethics and AI: cultural heritage, computer science and digital education. They brought together practitioners, researchers, and policymakers to discuss opportunities, risks, and strategies for integrating AI into heritage safeguarding.

Key insights highlight that AI can assist in documentation, digital reconstruction, metadata management, and public engagement. However, risks of misrepresentation, data loss, and unequal access were stressed, along with the urgent need for preparedness rather than reactive responses. Citizen engagement and community capacity emerged as essential factors in resilience, particularly in crisis zones such as Ukraine.

Across discussions, a four-phase framework – **mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery** – was identified as central to cultural heritage safeguarding. AI and citizen science play complementary roles in each stage, from preventive digitisation to post-crisis recovery.

1. Introduction

The AISTER project is a European Erasmus+ initiative that unites partners from five countries – the University of Latvia, University of Luxembourg, Web2Learn (Greece), Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, and Europeana Foundation. Its purpose is to explore how AI and citizen science can be combined to protect and preserve cultural heritage in times of crisis, from armed conflicts to natural disasters.

The project works on two levels: developing practical tools and methods for heritage protection, and embedding these themes into higher education to train a new generation of professionals. Special attention is given to the war in Ukraine as an urgent case, offering both a real-world laboratory for technological solutions and a stark reminder of what is at stake.

The project's core objectives are:

- Leveraging AI for documentation, analysis, and preservation of cultural heritage at risk.
- Strengthening university capacity to train professionals in these areas.
- Building bridges between cultural institutions, civil society, and technology sectors.
- Maintaining a people-centered, ethics-first approach to AI adoption.

This synthesis consolidates discussions from the three WP2A2 expert online roundtables held by the partners of the AISTER project in 2025. Each roundtable brought together practitioners, researchers, and policy actors to explore the intersection of artificial intelligence (AI), cultural heritage preservation, and public engagement during times of crisis. The sessions were hosted by:

- Web2Learn – '[AI Ethics and Cultural Heritage](#)', highlighting responsible AI use and participatory approaches (May 6, 2025), moderated Kateryna Boichenko;
- University of Luxembourg – 'AI and Ethics in Cultural Heritage: Opportunities, Risks and Responsibilities', examining the ethical frameworks – such as transparency, accountability, cultural sensitivity, and data sovereignty (May 26, 2025), moderated by Tugce Karatas.
- University of Latvia – '[Rescuing Cultural Heritage in Times of Crisis](#)', focusing on practical crisis management and capacity building (May 28, 2025), moderated by Uldis Zariņš.

While contexts and emphases varied, all three shared a common concern: how to safeguard tangible and intangible heritage under threat, harnessing technological tools without compromising ethical principles or community agency.

2. Context and Goals

Across all three roundtables, participants framed their discussion within the urgent challenge of safeguarding cultural heritage during emergencies – armed conflict, natural disasters, or societal crises – while integrating AI and citizen engagement in ways that are both effective and ethical. The war in Ukraine was a constant reference point, offering real-world urgency and a testbed for tools and strategies. As Research Infrastructure Coordinator at the IR* Huma-Num (CNRS) and the Officer for National Coordination at DARIAH ERIC Edward Gray noted, “There’s a war going on, and part of the Russian strategy is to deny the existence of and to eliminate Ukrainian identity. Thus, it is essential to preserve this heritage that is very much at risk.” (UNILU Roundtable).

3. Opportunities of AI for Cultural Heritage

3.1. Documentation and Recovery

AI facilitates rapid mapping and condition assessment of heritage sites, drawing on satellite imagery, media monitoring, and automated photographic comparison. In the case of damaged Ukrainian sites, UNESCO-supported initiatives combine AI image recognition with manual verification. As heritage preservation and digitization expert Māris Kaļinka pointed out, “We can’t fully train AI in crises because it requires thousands of examples – so we work with smaller, trustworthy datasets” (UL Roundtable)

3D reconstruction from photographs (e.g., Polycam, Backup Ukraine) enables the creation of digital twins of damaged or inaccessible heritage. Such tools operate effectively with minimal equipment and are therefore well suited to fieldwork in dangerous or resource-poor environments.

3.2. Data Management and Accessibility

AI tools enable the standardization of metadata, the cleaning and linking of large datasets, and improved accessibility for underfunded museums and archives. Such tools save time and reduce errors in cataloguing. Machine learning also helps process massive archival material emerging during crises – a challenge described by Jenny Kwok, Research Assistant Professor in the Faculty of Arts at the University of Hong Kong, as essential to “dealing with records that emerge all around the world at the same time, in a very diffuse way” (UNILU Roundtable).

3.3. Enhanced Interpretation and Engagement

Generative AI offers the potential to visualize absent or undocumented heritage elements, but requires a clear separation between authentic historical sources and interpretive reconstructions to avoid misinformation. As art historian and archaeologist Kamila Oles explained, “We used AI tools to enhance the quality of fragile Civil War photographs but took

care not to mislead audiences about what was historical evidence” (W2L Roundtable). The discussion highlighted that interpretive reconstructions can be powerful tools for education and advocacy – particularly when engaging audiences unfamiliar with the original context but only if accompanied by transparent documentation of methods, and disclosure of speculative elements. Without these safeguards, well-intentioned enhancements risk eroding trust in heritage records and confusing future researchers.

4. Risks and Ethical Dilemmas

4.1. Misrepresentation and Data Integrity

AI-generated imagery carries the risk of blurring fact and fiction if provenance metadata is lost. Kamila Oles also warned that “Once published online, the metadata distinguishing AI-generated images from originals could be lost... potentially misleading future audiences” (W2L Roundtable). Such loss can occur even in well-intentioned projects, undermining trust and complicating verification. Participants stressed the need for clear labelling, watermarking, and persistent metadata to safeguard the integrity of heritage records across platforms and over time.

4.2. Preparedness vs. Opportunistic Response

A recurrent theme across the roundtables was that many institutions seek digital preservation or safeguarding solutions only after irreversible damage has occurred – a point repeatedly described as “too late” for effective intervention. Emergency expert Jānis Vanags emphasized that “If mitigation measures had been in place, some lives – and heritage – could have been saved” (UL Roundtable). The Latvian and Ukrainian cases illustrated that ad hoc responses in crisis conditions – with limited staff, disrupted infrastructure, and shifting priorities – cannot compensate for the absence of pre-crisis measures. Participants stressed that preparedness must be understood not as a static plan, but as an embedded organisational culture encompassing preventive documentation, distributed storage strategies, role assignments, and trusted community networks. Without these elements in place, even well-intentioned post-event rescue efforts risk becoming fragmented, inefficient, and in some cases, impossible.

4.3. Unequal Capacity and Access

Many heritage institutions and communities lack the resources, skills, or infrastructure to use AI effectively. Without targeted support, the benefits of AI risk concentrating among well-resourced actors, leaving smaller institutions and grassroots initiatives behind. Over-reliance on large proprietary models limits inclusion, whereas smaller, open-source solutions – adaptable to local languages, cultural contexts, and modest infrastructure – were highlighted as more sustainable. Participants also stressed the value of ongoing training and cooperation between institutions to strengthen long-term capacity.

5. Citizen Engagement and Community Capacity

In crises, only a fraction of planned human resources are available making the role of local communities critical. NGOs leader, public speaker and activist Inese Vaivare observed that “Communities surrounding cultural institutions are particularly important... A cultural institution can play a key role in preparing its community for a crisis” (UL Roundtable). Training and mobilising these communities before emergencies, e.g., positioning cultural centers as community hubs and emergency shelters, was seen as an effective way to strengthen resilience.

Citizen scientists could play a significant role in the collection, verification, and annotation of heritage data, particularly in areas that are inaccessible to professionals due to conflict, disaster, or logistical constraints. Collaborative mapping, oral history collection, and crowdsourced photography can feed into official archives if guided by clear standards. Jenny Kwok highlighted that “Without awareness, the ownership of data equates to control of historical narratives” (UNILU Roundtable). This observation points to the need for participatory frameworks that not only guide data quality but also ensure that contributing communities retain an informed and substantive role in the governance and interpretation of the records they help to create.

6. Frameworks for Crisis–Stage Action

Across the roundtables, speakers described heritage protection in crises as a process that unfolds in distinct but interlinked phases. While terminology varied, discussions pointed to four broad stages:

Mitigation – reducing risk through advance planning, infrastructure adaptation, and early digitisation of vulnerable materials.

Preparedness – establishing risk assessment protocols, allocating resources, and maintaining prioritisation lists, alongside training staff and community partners in relevant tools and procedures.

Response – coordinating rescue and documentation during the crisis, including rapid digital preservation, decentralised reporting, and AI-assisted verification of damage.

Recovery – restoring damaged heritage, ensuring secure long-term storage, and re-engaging the public through accessible formats and interpretive initiatives.

Public participation and AI play distinct roles at each stage:

- Mitigation/Preparedness: risk modelling, digital catalogues, training citizens.
- Response: crowdsourced reporting from the field, AI-supported verification of damage reports.

- Recovery: AI-assisted restoration, digital access, interpretive exhibitions.

7. Reflections and Cross-Cutting Insights

Several speakers urged rethinking AI as more than just a technical tool. Taras Nazaruk, Head of Digital History Projects at the Center for Urban History, suggested, “We should not consider AI only as a tool... Cultural heritage could also be a useful insight for thinking conceptually about what AI is” (UNILU Roundtable). This reciprocal relationship where heritage perspectives can inform AI design was echoed in all three events.

Additional recurring points included:

- Balancing speed and rigor: emergencies demand rapid action, but not at the expense of ethical safeguards.
- Embedding ethics in training: both current professionals and students need the ability to assess AI outputs with a critical understanding of context, provenance, and limitations.
- Ensuring interoperability: heritage collections of diverse origin and format should be supported by compatible metadata standards and open access frameworks.
- Recognising irreversibility – in some cases, the only viable preservation outcome will be a digital surrogate.

8. Recommendations from the Roundtables

- Integrate AI ethics into heritage-related curricula to equip future professionals with the skills and judgement needed for responsible application.
- Strengthen community resilience by positioning cultural institutions as hubs for crisis preparedness and response.
- Promote the development of small-scale, open, and domain-specific AI models for heritage to ensure accessibility, affordability, and cultural relevance.
- Implement robust provenance and content-labelling standards for AI-generated or AI-enhanced heritage reconstructions.
- Support sustained international knowledge exchange between cultural heritage professionals, technologists, and civil society actors.

- Prioritise the digitisation of at-risk heritage collections before they are threatened by crisis conditions and ensure that they are securely preserved for the future.